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Annual International Journal on Analysis of Contemporary Legal Affairs (AIJACLA) is an annual international double-blind peer-reviewed journal in the field of law. The journal deals with contemporary affairs primarily within the discipline of law but also encourages interdisciplinary research works from any discipline provided the relation of the subject-matter with the legal institutions, legal instruments, or any other legal matters shall be established and highlighted to meet the eligibility criteria of the journal.

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4. Any other immoral, offensive, comments, or comments against any established custom or culture.

OBJECTIVES

1. To provide a platform for Indian Legal Professionals including Judges, Academicians, Advocates, and Students for showcasing their research skills;
2. To build an endeavor of research and analytical altitude amongst the young legal professionals under the experience and guidance of the senior legal experts;
3. To highlight the possible developments needed in the area of law through research and analytical spirits;
4. To encourage the habit of critical analysis and argumentative behavior amongst the law students; and
5. To help in policy formulation and legal drafting in India by expressing suggestions brought forward through research skills.

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Let us now examine the other side of the coin whether the Anti-Defection Law is a boon for securing the integrity of the political party. Articles 102(1)(e) and 191(1)(e) enable Parliament to formulate provisions for disqualification of an MP or MLA. Since contesting an election is just a statutory right and not a fundamental right, the Parliament is empowered to force such limitations as it thinks about essential or reasonable in the public interest.²¹

The passing of the Anti-defection Bill in both the Houses of the Parliament without a solitary vote of contradiction exhibits the exigency of the law to prevent defections. As a Member represents his whole constituency, it would fundamentally imply that the Members of the House speak to the desire of individuals and in that sense, the Anti-Defection Law is considered to have been formulated with the consistent will of the entire country. How then such a measure can be said to have the impact of disintegrating Parliamentary democracy.

significance of the political parties

For the effective functioning of the Parliament, political parties are indispensable.²² To elucidate the importance of a political party, Professor Harold opined that the Member's task is to support the general directions of his party. If he has so nice a conscience that a scrupulous examination of mostly

technical minutes is the necessary preamble to his vote, the correct remark upon his mentality is that he is not by disposition fit to be a Member the House.²³ The political stability of a party relies upon the mutual convictions and united actions of its Members. Any divided belief would result in impairing public confidence in it, which is its ultimate source of survival. Griffith and Ryle said:

"Loyalty to party is the norm, being based on shared beliefs. A divided party is looked on with suspicion by the electorate. . . . Generally, Members will accept majority decisions in the party even when they disagree. It is understandable therefore that a Member who rejects the party whip even on a single occasion will attract attention and more criticism than sympathy. To abstain

²¹ Ministry of Home Affairs, Report of Committee on Defections (1969).

²² Kanhiya Lal Omar v. R.K. Trivedi, 4 S.C.C. 628 (1985).

²³ Harold Joseph Laski, PARLIAMENTARY GOVERNMENT IN ENGLAND: A COMMENTARY (1938).

*from voting when required by a party to vote is to suggest a degree of unreliability. To vote against party is disloyalty. To join with others in abstention or voting with the other side smacks of conspiracy."*²⁴

The Parliament/State Legislature is composed of parties and not individual Members. The Government is free to exercise control over its Members. To defy the Government would be equivalent to leaving the party.²⁵ If the Parliament/Legislature comprises only of independent members without any party or few small parties, then no Government could have been sustained.

The electors, along these lines, do not give their vote to a candidate but generally to a party. The candidate's electioneering is very less significant in comparison to the impact which his party makes on the brains of the electors. The Member is thus returned to support a party.²⁶ The constituents

²⁴ Supra note 15.

²⁵ Ivor Jennings, CABINET GOVERNMENT (1959).

²⁶ Supra note 23.

anticipate that the Member should adhere to the guidelines of the party's whip.²⁷

freedom of speech is not violated

Paragraph 2(1) of the Tenth Schedule offers an impact to the rule and assumption of the integrity of the party by imposing disqualification on Members. In *Kihoto Hollohan*,²⁸ the Hon'ble Supreme Court has construed that 'any direction' should pertain to two matters, viz., (i) a vote on the decision of the motion of confidence or no confidence in the government; and (ii) if the impugned motion is related to a fundamental policy of the political party dependent on which it moved toward the electorate. The same has also been suggested by the Dinesh Goswami Committee on Electoral Reforms.²⁹

When the party proposes a Bill, it is anticipated to have been discussed where the Members of the House get a full opportunity to set up their perspectives. Once the party comes to a final decision, the Member is bound to comply with it. If still, the Member cannot accommodate, he can surrender the seat to which he got chosen in the name of the party and look for re-election. So far as the

²⁷ Herman Finer, THEORY AND PRACTICE OF MODERN GOVERNMENT 97 (1949).

²⁸ *Kihoto Hollohan v. Zachillhu*, 1992 S.C.C. Supl. (2) 651, at 711.

²⁹ Government of India, Ministry of Law and Justice, Legislative Department, Report of the Committee on Electoral Reforms (Sep. 2020, 07, 10:00 AM), <https://adrindia.org/sites/default/files/Dinesh%20Goswami%20Report%20on%20Electoral%20Reforms.pdf>.

right of a Member under Articles 105(1) and 194(1) is concerned, these rights are not unconditional but are dependent upon different provisions of the Constitution such as Article 19 and rules of the Parliament. The Constitution makers, accordingly, never proposed to give any supreme right of freedom of speech to a Member of the Parliament/State Legislature and it can be supervised and regulated by enacting separate Constitutional legislation.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The purpose of enacting the Anti-Defection Law is not only to provide stability to the Government but also to make it effective. Democracy is a basic feature of the Constitution. Election directed at standard spans is basic to the democratic system conceived in the Constitution. At the same time, the sanctity of the electoral process also needs to be secured. If a Member casts a vote or refrains from casting a vote by going against the directions and ethics of the political party then it would be equivalent to dissatisfaction with regards to the program dependent on which the Member and got himself chosen by the electorates and would result in the breach of the trust of the electorate.

The debate is a basic and sound need in the working of Parliamentary democracy and considering the outcomes of the disqualification which is the termination of the Membership of a House, the *Kihoto* case has rightly limited the freedom of speech

without eliminating it since freedom of speech is also indispensable in democracy along with a stable political party. Such limitation is viable with the soul of our Parliamentary Constitution and for compelling and intentional administration of the nation, individual freedom of Individuals from the House must be diminished in the interest of the nation.

The research paper provides few suggestions given below to harmonize both the aspects as both are wheels of the same vehicle which aids in the smooth and effective functioning of Parliamentary democracy which is one of the basic features of the Constitution:

- i. Paragraph 2(1) should be interpreted amicably with other Constitutional provisions and should be suitably limited to the objects of the Tenth Schedule.
- ii. When the impugned motion is regarding the impeachment of the President of India and Judges of the Supreme Court, no directions should be issued to its Members since the exercise of these functions are essentially judicial.
- iii. Where a Member defects for a financial preferred position, a component of exacerbation goes into his activity which must be dealt with more noteworthy seriousness. Such legislator shall be barred from contesting an election in the future. This

is necessary as defections have not stopped altogether. Such suggestion may appear to be harsh at the first glance, but to create a deterrence effect among the Members, it is expedient as malignant diseases call for drastic remedies.

SECTION (B) ARTICLE

CONTEMPT OF COURT: AN URGENT REQUISITE TO RE-EXPLORE

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ABSTRACT

The laws on contempt of court, the most controversial issue, has once again been put in the dock, over their incompetency to elucidate the wafer-thin distinction of contempt of court with the right to speech and expression and the magnanimity of them that have given people the courage and a chance to lower the prestige of judges and courts and to undermine the integrity and devotion of judges and the judicial system of India. The sanctity of the distinction between Freedom of Speech and Contempt of Court lies in the unabated occurrences of Contempt of Court in India. This paper deals with the pressing need of making the laws stringent on the contempt of court and the necessity of setting a model before all, to hamper the events of bringing down the poise and authority of the courts.

KEYWORDS

Contempt, Freedom of Speech, Judiciary, and Supreme Court

INTRODUCTION

Contempt of Court, the most controversial issue, has once again come into the limelight, this time, by the tweets of Prashant Bhushan. Time and again, the voices have been raised to elucidate and ratify the wafer-thin difference between Right to Speech and

Expression and Contempt of Court. Contempt of Court is defined under Contempt of Courts Act, 1971, seems unclear, as there occur unabated instances of contempt in India wherein the thin line between free speech and contempt of court has been constantly jumped and disrespected.

Contempt of Court alludes to the offense of irreverence or insubordination towards a courtroom and its officials that contradicts or challenges the equity, authority, and poise of the court. Contempt of Court, as a protected force, is vested with the Supreme Court, giving the Apex Court, power under Article 129 of the Constitution of India to punish the offenders for the contempt of itself¹. Article 129 of the Indian Constitution states that “*The Supreme Court of India shall be a court of record and will have all the forces of such a court including the ability to rebuff for contempt of itself*”². The High Court too, under Article 215 of the Indian Constitution has been empowered to punish the people for contempt of itself³. While a fundamental thought of a contempt law is to rebuff the individuals, who don't regard the sets of the courts, in the Indian Law, hatred is likewise used to rebuff those whose discourse brings down the nobility of the court and meddles with the organization of equity.

UNABATED INSTANCES OF CONTEMPT OF COURT IN INDIA

The instances of contempt of courts in India continue unabated. It is not for the first time that a person like Prashant Bhushan was tried before the Apex Court for disrespect of the Court or its officers. The

¹ Contempt of Court: Time for a relook?, Clear IAS, (Oct. 2020, 05, 09:00 AM), <https://www.clearias.com/contempt-of-court/>.

² Constitution of India 1950, Art. 129.

³ Constitution of India 1950, Aart. 215.

antiquity of these instances can be long traced. Moreover, it is also not the first time for Prashant Bhushan to commit this offense. In 2009 also he had made allegations of corruption on former Chief Justices while giving an interview to Tehelka Magazine, whose proceedings are still pending before the Apex Court⁴.

There have been several high-profile cases of contempt in India in the last two decades. For instance, M.V.Jayarajan, a politician from Kerala's Communist Party of India, was imprisoned for four weeks by the Apex Court for using the Malayalam term, ‘human’(idiot) in a speech criticizing the judiciary⁵. Another instance, when a politician was punished for contempt of court can be found is in the case of EMS Namboodiripad, when in a speech criticizing the judiciary, he asserted that the Communist theorists like Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels had considered the judiciary to be an “*instrument of oppression*”⁶.

Moreover, in 2002, a popular writer and activist Arundhati Roy was held guilty for contempt of court

⁴ Bhandra Sinha, SC refuses to accept Prashant Bhushan's explanation in 2009 contempt case, The Print, (Oct. 2020, 10, 01:14 PM), <https://theprint.in/judiciary/sc-refuses-to-accept-prashant-bhushans-explanation-in-2009-contempt-case/478540/>.

⁵ Prashant Reddy & Kian Ganz, A guide to contempt law, Mint, (Oct. 2020, 11, 02:00 PM), <https://www.livemint.com/Politics/vwdCg7zPRgLANLWwNvPl eO/A-guide-to-contempt-law.html>.

⁶ Should the courts be above scrutiny: Debate rekindles with politician jailed for calling judge an idiot, The News Minute <https://www.thenewsminute.com/article/should-courts-be-above-scrutiny-debate-rekindles-politician-jailed-calling-judge-idiot-23082>.

after she avowed that the judiciary was “*smothering contradiction*”, in an article titled ‘The Great Common Good’⁷.

The legal system in India too is not able to sojourn the disseminating instances of contempt of court in India. Despite the judgments being pronounced time and again by the Apex Court concerning the contempt of court, they are hardly able to make an impact on the continuance of instances of lowering the prestige of judges and courts. Still, the government of India has turned a deaf ear to the vital need of amending the Contempt of Courts Act, 1971.

ANTIQUITY BEHIND RECKONING CONTEMPT OF COURT UNDER ARTICLE 19 OF INDIAN CONSTITUTION

From the very beginning, when the talks on adding contempt of court as a curtailment to the freedom of speech and expression were hot in the constituent assembly, the views bifurcated. While some members were against the amendment proposed by T.T. Krishnamachari for adding contempt of court in restrictions under Article 19, some sustained the amendment.

⁷ A. G. NOORANI, A case for a new approach to contempt of court, *The Hindu*, (Oct. 2020, 11, 10:30 AM), <https://frontline.thehindu.com/cover-story/a-case-for-a-new-approach/article32422986.ece>.

The views were two folded. R.K. Sidhva, a member of the Constituent Assembly, criticized the assumption that the judges will use the law cautiously with a view that “*Judges have not got two horns; they also are liable to commit mistakes. For what reason would it be a good idea for us to show such a great amount of tolerance to them? The interest of the public must be safeguarded*”. Biswanath Das has even gone to the extent, terming the very move to table the amendment as ‘*tyranny of the drafting committee*’.

Positioning the amendment as filling a lacuna rather than expanding the scope of Article 19, T.T. Krishnamachari was of the view that “*as contempt of court law was already in existence, as was the case with defamation and public order provisions, it had to be expressly protected from being overwritten by the final Article 13*”. Moreover, Ambedkar’s response to the whole debate rested on legal technicalities. He was of the view that if contempt of court is not added as a reasonable restriction, the contempt laws would have to be abrogated as they would conflict with the fundamental rights chapter.

Finally, after a bit of wrangling and the exchange of views, the amendment was adopted by the constituent assembly with the subject of contempt of